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Science Product Pipelines and Archive Architecture for the DART Mission

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Extended Abstract — On September 26, 2022, the Double Asteroid Redirection Test (DART) mission was the first successful demonstration of a kinetic impactor for planetary defense. The DART mission utilized a novel data processing pipeline architecture to quickly produce and analyze the quality of raw and calibrated images from the camera mounted on-board the spacecraft. These data products were used in conjunction with data from LICIACube and data from ground observatories to characterize the impact site and to determine the effectiveness of using a kinetic impactor for planetary defense.

The DART Mission: The Double Asteroid Redirection Test (DART) mission successfully demonstrated technology for kinetic deflection of an asteroid for planetary defense [1-4]. The lone instrument onboard the DART spacecraft was the Didymos Reconnaissance and Asteroid Camera for Opnav (DRACO) [5], which obtained over 250,000 images during its charge. The DART Science Operations Center (SOC) utilized a novel automated data processing pipeline to produce raw and calibrated DRACO images for analysis and visualization, and a semi-automated pipeline to track image quality metrics from all images taken by DRACO over the course of the mission. This allowed for ongoing processing and analysis during flight to prepare for rendezvous with the Didymos system, and efficient operations in the SOC during the impact event.

The DRACO instrument produced a large volume of data at an extremely high rate with variable imaging modes and targets, which required rapid processing and analysis and “scientist in the loop” decision making. During the impact event, the processing pipeline was fed images of interest identified by the SOC to prioritize calibration of the most visually and scientifically rich images (e.g., Fig. 1).

Figure 1: A view of the asteroid Dimorphos, oriented with its north pole toward the top of the image. DART’s onboard DRACO imager captured this image from a distance of 68 kilometers. Dimorphos is roughly 160 meters in length. This figure was modified from an image identified in real time as the last frame to contain all of the lit body of Dimorphos in the field of view [1].

DRACO Pipeline Architecture: Downlinked images and housekeeping telemetry were unpacked by the DART Mission Operations Center (MOC) and passed to the Science Operations Center (SOC). These files were autonomously formatted and calibrated to create data products that are compliant with NASA’s Planetary Data System (PDS) archive requirements. These data products were then semi-autonomously analyzed to provide image quality metrics for the Investigation Team. The data processing pipeline and analysis pipeline were implemented in Nextflow [6, 7], which

allowed for parallelization of Python and Java tools developed by the SOC. Processing algorithms were vectorized where possible, allowing the data processing pipeline to produce approximately 25 raw images per second and 15 calibrated images per second.

Optimization and parallelization of the data processing pipeline allowed the final 150 images prior to impact to be calibrated and delivered to the Investigation Team and the press within 15 minutes after the impact. The image quality analysis pipeline allowed for rapid identification of detector misconfigurations, missing data, and other adverse events. The DRACO software architecture and automation implementation are outlined here as a framework for future missions, with an emphasis on planetary defense applications.

Data Processing Pipeline: The autonomous DRACO data processing pipeline registered incoming MOC products to a SQL database. This database contained a table that tracked each MOC file with their associated raw product, raw product creation time, calibrated product, and calibrated product creation time. The processing pipeline queried the table on an adjustable time delta set by the cron command-line utility to find MOC files that did not have associated raw data products in the SOC. These records were fetched in batches where the number of files ingested could be modified in a configuration file used by the pipeline, which was also used to set parameters such as allocation of computing resources for multithreading and multiprocessing.

Software was developed to format MOC files into raw SOC data products, which are Flexible Image Transport (FITS) format files with metadata information stored in the header. The metadata stored in each FITS header includes calibration information such as detector temperature, spacecraft geometry calculated from SPICE, and information from DART’s autonomous navigation software, SMARTNav [8]. Once the new SOC raw products were created and registered to the DRACO database table with their creation time, the processing pipeline queried the table again to find any raw product records that did not have associated calibrated products.

The processing pipeline rejected raw files where the observation type was identified as a dark, bias, or test pattern image based on FITS header keywords, as well as images affected by detector reconfiguration and partial header information. Software was developed to radiometrically calibrate data products into either radiance or I/F values based on the image target and mission phase header keywords. The SPICE-derived geometry values in the FITS headers were used for I/F calculations when applicable. A second table in the DRACO database was used to correlate calibration information based on timestamp, detector temperature, exposure time, and other key metrics fetched from the raw FITS header metadata. Upon processing pipeline completion, calibrated images were registered to the DRACO database with their creation time, and the pipeline would idle until the next time delta passed.

In addition to searching for unprocessed MOC files, the processing pipeline also queried the database for records where the raw product creation time was newer than the calibrated product creation time. A newer time indicated that a newer version of a raw image existed, and the calibrated image should be reprocessed. The DRACO data processing pipeline was extremely efficient and virtually hands-free from end-to-end, although the pipeline could still be manually run using command line scripts for troubleshooting and calibration verification.

Image Quality Analysis Pipeline: The vast number of images taken by DRACO made it impractical to rely on humans to identify image quality issues. For example, some observation sequences acquired more than 16,000 images in the span of several hours. The DRACO image quality analysis pipeline was a collection of Python scripts that semi-autonomously collected statistics on image quality metrics requested by the instrument scientists.

Image quality statistics were stored in CSV format alongside MOC housekeeping data and used to fill out an HTML document template that created internally-accessible webpages on SOC servers (Fig. 2). A Python script was used to compare the most recent raw and calibrated product creation dates to the image quality stats file creation date and determine if the CSV file needed to be updated. This pipeline is referred to as “semi-autonomous” as the image analysis scripts were run in job manager bash scripts using the cron command-line utility, however, individual scripts were frequently deployed to implement new analyses and refresh the webpage.

year	day	mission phase	total images	# partial images	# bad images	# of files not _01.fits	# of Radiance files	# of I/F files
2022	269	terminal	13399	0	0	0	0	13399
2022	269	approach	2789	3	0	0	2789	0
2022	269	final	236	1	0	0	0	236
2022	267	approach	2508	1	0	0	2508	0
2022	266	approach	1237	0	0	0	1237	0
2022	265	approach	1237	0	0	0	1237	0
2022	264	approach	1237	0	0	0	1237	0
2022	263	approach	989	0	0	0	989	0
2022	262	approach	248	0	0	0	248	0
2022	260	approach	1237	0	0	0	1237	0
2022	259	approach	1196	1	0	0	1196	0

Figure 2: An excerpt of the image quality analysis table for calibrated data products used by the SOC to identify partial images, bad images, and potential split images. These statistics were collected from common keywords in DRACO FITS file headers and organized by Day of Year (DOY) and mission phase.

Header metadata from raw and calibrated FITS files were parsed to determine metrics such as missing keywords, timing inconsistencies based on SPICE-derived values, partial images, and images split between two or more files. Files that were identified as “split images”, where two or more files contained subsets of data for a whole image, were then

reprocessed by the MOC to stitch together a single full image. For raw products, the image data were analyzed for maximum and minimum DN levels above or below user-specified thresholds to identify detector reconfigurations and bad images.

PDS Archiving: The DRACO data processing pipeline produced products and labels that were formatted to be compliant with NASA's Planetary Data System (PDS) archiving standards. The PDS is used as the long-term archive for storing all of the mission data products. The data products to be archived include image products generated from DRACO; products from the LICIACube Explorer Imaging for Asteroid (LEIA) and LICIACube Unit Key Explorer (LUKE) instruments hosted on the LICIACube spacecraft; and products generated by the Lowell, Magdalena Ridge, Las Cumbres, and Las Campanas ground observatories. Ancillary information in the form of Spacecraft, Planetary, Instrument, C-kernel, and Ephemeris (SPICE) kernels and radio science products will also be archived. Finally, shape models and derived data products created from the shape models will be part of the PDS archive. The following is an overview of the PDS data that will be available to the general scientific community.

DRACO Data Archive: The DRACO data archive contains all the raw and calibrated images generated during flight, as well as the calibration files used to generate the calibrated images. The DRACO instrument took over 250,000 raw images during flight, of which over 245,000 images were calibrated (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Calibrated image of the last full frame taken by DRACO before impact. North is to the lower left.

Several of the calibration files were updated post-launch; all versions of the calibration files are included in the PDS archive.

Calibrated image files containing geometry backplanes will be archived once the Shape Model

products have been finalized. Backplanes are only generated for images collected during the Final mission phase and consist of a set of location, illumination, and geometric parameters calculated at each DRACO pixel center that intersects Dimorphos.

LICIACube Data Archive: The LICIACube spacecraft is a 6U CubeSat that was hosted by the DART spacecraft and deployed 15 days before DART impacted the Didymos asteroid. LICIACube was to witness the impact and acquire images for about 10 minutes around the time of impact (Fig 4).

Figure 4: LUKE image taken a few minutes after DART impact.

The LEIA camera hosted by LICIACube is a CMOS sensor with a 2048x2048 pixel array. LEIA is designed to acquire images from long distances (close approach at approximately 50km from Dimorphos). The LUKE camera is a CMOS sensor with a 2048x1088 pixel array. It contains a Bayer color filter, allowing it to generate RGB color images. The LICIACube archive will include all the LUKE and LEIA raw and calibrated images and the calibration files used to generate the calibrated images.

Radio Science Archive: Radio signals emitted by the DART and LICIACube spacecraft are collected by the Deep Space Network (DSN) and provided to the DART mission as spacecraft tracking data. The Radio Science dataset includes the DSN tracking and navigation files, the ionosphere calibration files, and the Maneuver Acceleration File (MAF). The MAF describes the DART thruster firings; this provides additional content for understanding the radio science data.

Shape Model Archive: Global Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) (Figure 5), impact site DTMs, and tilt maps will be archived. The DTMs and tilt maps are generated from DRACO images using stereophotoclinometry (SPC). Other shape model products include the

Asteroid Center of Figure, body coordinate systems, pole location, and rotation period. Spacecraft position and observational geometry derived using the highest resolution Dimorphos shape model will be used to generate the DRACO backplanes.

Figure 5: Preliminary Dimorphos Global DTM as viewed along its principal axes [1].

Ground Observatories: Data from the ground observations are organized by observatory. Each observatory dataset will include the raw and calibrated image data and the derived data in the form of photometric light curve tables. Additional data include master calibration files and reference star images. While details of image calibration, light curve format, and the data generation process vary across the observatories, the organization of the data into raw, calibrated, and derived collections remains the same. This was done to standardize the datasets from each telescope as much as possible.

SPICE: The SPICE dataset consists of ancillary data files known as SPICE kernels. The kernels contain information such as the spacecraft, planet, and asteroid ephemerides, orientations, sizes, and shapes. Other kernels describe the instrument orientation with respect to the host spacecraft, and the instrument field of view. SPICE kernels are archived with the PDS Navigation and Ancillary Information (NAIF) node. Software provided by NAIF in conjunction with the SPICE kernels allows users to determine observation geometry, such as spacecraft location and orientation, instrument pointing and target location.

Future Work: The DART Investigation Team continues to analyze and reprocess images post-impact to provide the best possible set of raw and calibrated products to the community. The initial DRACO archive delivery has been made available via the PDS, including documentation of calibration performed by the data processing pipeline.

The processing and analysis software architecture and automation framework developed during this mission will be generifed and adopted for future missions, to enable rapid product generation and “scientist in the loop” decision making for semi-automated analysis tasks. A subset of these tools will

be publicly released as part of the Small Body Mapping Tool [9]. The ability to analyze products in near real time while continuously downlinking and processing data is particularly relevant for planetary defense, where both efficiency and accuracy are critical for mission success.

References:

[1] Daly, R.T. et al (2023) *Nature*, doi: 10.1038/s41586-023-05810-5.
 [2] Thomas, C.A. et al. (2023) *Nature*, doi:10.1038/s41586-023-05805-2.
 [3] Li, J.-Y. et al. (2023), *Nature* doi: 10.1038/s41586-023-05811-4
 [4] Cheng, A.F. et al. (2023) *Nature*, doi: 10.1038/s41586-023-05878-z
 [5] Fletcher Z.J. et al. (2022) *Proc. SPIE*, 12180.
 [6] Di Tommaso P. et al. (2017) *Nature Biotechnology*, 35, 316–319.
 [7] Heyd R.S. et al. (2019) *4th Planetary Data Workshop*, Abstract #2151.
 [8] Chen M.H. et al. (2018) *Advances in the Astronautical Sciences*, 164, 347–359.
 [9] Steele R.J. et al. (2023), *54th Lunar and Planetary Science Conference*, Abstract #2728.